

Assessing the sensory experience of product design: Towards a method for ‘Five Senses Testing’

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Abstract

This paper presents and discusses a method using a range of techniques for assessing sensorial perception of product design and interaction. Collectively denoted ‘Five Senses Testing’, the purpose of the method is to facilitate the assessment of sensory experience related to product design and product use. Furthermore, the outcomes of using the techniques inform product design development by connecting the sensory response to product features and characteristics. A range of explorative activities were undertaken to inform the development of the method and techniques used to elicit sensory feedback from product and use examination and assessment for design purposes. Through trials involving design students and design professionals, the method has been elaborated, tested and evaluated in focus group and industrial workshop sessions with a range of respondents to elicit individual sensory responses and experiences of products. Insights from method use with various products and use contexts and feedback from respondents show that the method is highly appreciated and valued as useful for assessment and design purposes.

Keywords: method, affective design, five senses, 5-senses, evaluation, assessment, product design, experience, sensory.

Introduction

A challenge during product design development is to assess and predict the effect of the emerging product on the senses and to design products in an informed manner with respect to sensory experiences. One reason is that during the early phases of design development, the product can only be represented at a very abstract, rudimentary level with as yet unresolved detail. In order to assess how the product will eventually be perceived by the senses, support is needed.

Experience with undergraduate design and graduate ergonomic students involved in product design projects found traditional methods used to gain information about the sensory qualities of products were cumbersome, time consuming and too often without significant effect. Techniques such as mood boards and visual product evaluation were found to be more readily accessible; however they did not provide a direct understanding of how the product affected the sensory aspect of the person/product experience. A new approach that more directly identifies and assesses sensory experience in a manner that makes it accessible for design was required. This observation led to the development of a method that can be used in multiple modes during the design process.

Sensory experiences and product design

Sensory perception is a basic mode of experiencing products and product use and is the basis of a pleasurable interaction with the product. Our senses are the first point of contact with the physical product, and therefore they should be a valuable source of information in the development and design of products.

Goldstein (2002) writes: “One purpose of perception is to inform us about properties of the environment that are important for our survival”. For the purposes of design, we may go so far as to say, that the role of sensory perception is to guide us to engage with products that look and feel safe, friendly or useful. However, perception and pleasure attained from sensorial stimuli is not the same for all – it is highly subjective, linked to the shifting aspects of individual, cultural and social variables. Moreover, it is dependent on sensory modalities governed by different individual perceptive

characteristics, which, in all, makes every sensory experience a highly individual affair (Bonapace, 2000). Surely, the development of a knowledge base about sensorial stimuli that cause these reactions is of benefit in design – and tools that inform us about these experiences in design processes even more so. The need for approaches that inform designers in making design decisions that are not only based on intuitive judgements and ‘educated guesses’ is often addressed (see, e.g., Liu, 2003).

Bonapace (2000) discusses the world around us as “a supplier of stimuli that reach people through sensory channels which triggers the stimulus and response mechanisms”. These response mechanisms include *input* (sensorial stimuli from the environment), *perception* (what the individual receives after stimuli passing through the person’s psycho-sensorial filters), *cognition* (related to elaboration and decision-making), *action* (the result of the decision), and *output* (the result of the action).

Sensory perception as part of the total product experience leads to a range of effects originating in products, including aesthetic, emotional and pleasurable responses. According to Hekkert (2006), product experience can be seen as “*the entire set of effects that is elicited by the interaction between a user and a product, including the degree to which all our senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meanings we attach to the product (experience of meaning), and the feelings and emotions that are elicited (emotional experience)*”. The method presented here focus on informing the ongoing design process based on the consideration and assessment of aesthetic, sensory experiences. The senses are the source of our aesthetic experience of the product – in fact, the original Greek word *aisthetikos* refers to ‘sense perception’ (Merriam-Webster, 2006). However, in the mid-eighteenth century the philosopher Baumgarten changed the meaning of the term into ‘philosophy of the beautiful’ (Burnham, 2006) or ‘sensuous delight’ (Goldman, 2001). Today, this is the generally accepted use of the concept of aesthetics. In fact, Hekkert (2006) proposes a definition of aesthetics which equates it with the pleasure attained from sensory perception.

Other authors discuss the senses in relation to the other parts of the product experience, especially that related to feelings and emotions. The movements of ‘pleasurable products’ (e.g., Jordan, 2000, 2002) and ‘emotional design’ (e.g., Desmet, 2002 and Norman, 2004) are based on the understanding of hedonic and

emotional benefits arising from the aesthetic and sensory pleasures associated with products. Jordan (2002) describes 'pleasure' as "*the emotional, hedonic and practical benefits associated with products and services*", and differentiates the types of pleasures into four categories: Physio-pleasure; Socio-pleasure; Psycho-pleasure; and Ideo-Pleasure. The senses directly inform Physio-pleasure, which includes pleasures connected with vision, touch, hearing, taste, and smell, but also kinaesthetic; our awareness of the body in space (Bonapace 2000). According to the work of Desmet (2002), emotions are a result of our assessment or appraisal of the product in light of our experience and concerns related to it. Sensory impressions thus give rise to emotions and therefore indirectly also inform the third pleasure according to Jordan; Psycho-pleasure, relating to cognitive demands and emotional reactions related to sensory perception. Therefore, understanding the sensory experience of products is a critical factor in being able to understand the subsequent appraisals that lead to emotional, and subsequently, to types of pleasurable response.

Towards Five Senses Testing

Our approach is based on using sensory response as a means of informing the ongoing design process. Based on the analysis of initial sensory experiences, our method aims to capture meanings and emotional response as well, provided that users' contexts, motives and moods are known. However, we are primarily interested in the sensory approach as a way of expanding our understanding of emergent concepts, addressing shortcomings and identifying opportunities for further concept development and refinement.

Based on our experiences from product design education, we are interested in an approach that allows us to assess the effect of the product's characteristics, features or attributes on our senses. Since we are concerned with using such an approach at the early stages of design, we acknowledge that this product does not have to be physically present in its entirety – it may, in fact, be in the form of a sketch, a simple rudimentary model, or any other type of representation of the product-to-be. The important thing is that the representation of the product allows for anyone involved in using the method to assess its effect on our senses, on any level of understanding. It really does not matter whether everyone involved understands the product to the same

level of detailing or refinement – any type of response or affect based on our sensory perception of the representation of the product or on our imaginary idea about the finalised product is valid. In fact, the more responses we get, the greater the amount of potentially useful information we have at our disposal for understanding and designing the product into something which is pleasurable to our senses – or avoiding designing something which potentially causes displeasure.

The objective of finding ways of informing the product design process through sensory experience and assessment has led to a number of techniques collectively denoted ‘Five Senses Testing’, which we describe in the following.

Technique 1: Sensory Experience Assessment

The objective of this technique is to develop an insight and understanding into how we experience real products through our senses. The technique is divided into two sequential parts: a pre-use examination; and an in-use assessment of sensory experiences. The purpose of these parts is to separate the sensory experiences and stimuli that result from differing contexts of product experience. This provides a differential understanding of sensory experience from the perceived design of the product prior to use and subsequently, the actual experience of the product in use.

Fifteen participants (5 female and 10 male) tried this technique as part of their undergraduate studies into affective product design. Groups of three were formed and completed the following activities using a feedback document:

A: Product examination prior to use

Group members are to verbalize their ‘five senses experience’ of the product. One person is to record the interactions for the group. This is in the form of annotations linked to images of the product (previously prepared for this purpose) on the feedback document.

B: Product assessment during use

Group members are all to use the product in context.

Subsequently group members discuss how to improve the product in a manner that would improve the ‘five senses experience’ by producing annotated sketches and short statements linked to individual senses (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of Product Assessment During Use.

Products provided for assessment included: a telephone; 2-stroke garden line trimmer; garden blower/vacuum; electric garden line trimmer and a wind-up radio.

Results

The technique provided direct assessment of the product through participatory experience. Most participants felt they had gained an insight into how products affect users in a manner they had previously not considered. For example, the group working with the 2-stroke line trimmer realised the product created noise and was loud, which lead to the conclusion that at least two groups would be considered negatively affected by the product: the primary subject – the user needing earmuffs to comfortably and safely use the product, and the secondary group - those in the vicinity of the user, being subjected to the disturbing noise of the product. The group investigating the garden blower/vacuum identified that the quality of experience when using the major control switch was poor and determined that the product should give a greater sense of control in adjustment.

Discussion

Having a section for each sense on the feedback document highlighted when a sense (usually smell and taste) was not used in providing feedback from the product experience. This prompted some students to recommend that the selection of senses sampled could be narrowed. In discussion it was noted that getting a 'nil' result could be just as useful as if it identified a possible sensory input that could be further utilised. Participants noted that part 'B' focused on improving the end-user sensory experience, which is quite a different approach to traditional techniques of design development that focus on the product first. It was noted most design activity revolved around the sense of sight, where as this technique forced the consideration of other sensory experience, enhancing the understanding of product/person interaction.

Technique 2: Sensory Snapshot

The objective of the technique is to describe a product interaction through a 'snapshot' of sensory sampling. This snapshot is a graphic representation of sensory experience (see Figure 2). Subsequently reviewing this snapshot allows for proposing a design consequence that has the potential for improved sensory experience. A reporting sheet was used to record outcomes. The activity involved the following steps:

1. Assessing a product for the quality of the elicited sensory experience and graphically representing this outcome on a star diagram.
2. Visualizing and stating descriptions of product experience for each of the senses, in relation to the product tested.
3. Transferring these descriptions into design consequence in the form of statements and sketches.
4. Subsequently developing design criteria from the previous activities.

Results and Discussion

Five participants (two female and three male) trailed this technique as part of their postgraduate studies in Ergonomics. Ages ranged from 25-55; all were students at Massey University. The technique provided direct analysis of the product through participatory experience. It was noted that using the star diagram easily allowed other

senses to be added if necessary, e.g., separating balance out from the sense of sound and adding this sense to product experiences that involved movement provided more focused sensory information in this area. Developing a description was found to be difficult without describing feelings associated with sensory experience. The design criteria developed were non-specific and tended to be about product aspiration.

Figure 2. Example of Sensory Snapshot

Technique 3: Experience Continuum Sampling

This technique seeks to provide more in-depth, specific information related to product features and experiences through sensory experience. The objective was to develop an approach that industrial participants could use in a straightforward manner to gain insight into sensory response related to their products. The technique involves a number of steps according to the following (see Figure 3):

1. Identify a range of product interactions along the product-person experience continuum.
2. Select from this range a stage (a specific activity of interaction) to sample.
3. Identify suitable respondents to test.
4. Implement the end-user trial and have the end-user complete the assessment.
This involves making assessments of the quality of sensory experience,

identifying the active feature of the product that provides the sensory experience, and commenting on the relationship between sensory information and active feature through a reflective comment.

5. Analyze the results to identify areas of further design/innovation activity.
6. Act on this analysis through design activity.

Figure 3. An example of Experience Continuum Sampling technique.

Results and Discussion

Versions of the technique were used in a series of workshops focusing on product innovation with industrial participants from product developing and manufacturing companies. The technique was altered after the first workshop to take into account feedback from participants and is presented in the updated format. Participants included manufacturing professionals from engineering, marketing, management and

design; academic staff and senior students from the Institute of Design for Industry and Environment and the Institute of Technology and Engineering at Massey University; and design researchers from AFFECT - The Centre for Affective Product Design at Massey University.

Participants used the technique to assess the sensory experience across a range of design projects. Themes included systems for intelligent houses, communication products, and temporary shelter design. Feedback from using the technique on the various projects was overwhelmingly positive, indicating the potential of the technique for addressing issues of sensory experience that were deemed useful for design. Most of the participants found the technique had good value with several noting it provided useful information that enhanced design potential. Positive response included comments such as: “Interesting, brought up ideas of new features for our product”, “Good to be able to go outside the square”, “Interesting, user centric - encourages use of otherwise ignored feedback from test subjects”, “Very tidy – a great way to summarize what we should be doing/and do on a daily basis”.

A few comments were non-committal or negative indicating a need for further development, e.g., “Not very applicable unless product is at final stage”, “It opened up new ways of looking at a product. But I felt it may have missed a few areas”.

Previously reported feedback from Technique 1, indicating that a reduction of the number of senses sampled might be useful for specific product areas, was also recorded. Feedback indicated that the technique requires a certain amount of imagination and extrapolation in terms of the appearance and the physical properties of the final product when used at the early sketching phases of the process. In addition, one of the participants questioned whether sensory evaluation should supersede functional elements.

Conclusions

By understanding the relationship between sensory input and the correlating aspects of our experience, we can better understand factors that affect the end-user product experience. This leads to clearer insight into the nature of the sensorial qualities of

product experience. It is then possible to intentionally develop these qualities to attain specified levels of affective and pleasurable experience.

‘Five Senses Testing’ uses a range of approaches to inform and advance the development of sensory qualities of products from ideation, through conceptualisation to post production end user trials. Usable by designers or product developers during the design development process, the method addresses the sensorial perception of the emerging product through the senses of sight, touch, hearing, smell, and taste. This method can be used as an in-house evaluation tool, or can involve users to provide evaluative feedback on proposed designs. The method can be used to assess early, abstract and un-detailed representations of the product, as well as more detailed and concrete product representations at later stages of the design process. Furthermore, it can be used proactively for defining important product properties and informing design specifications, as well as reactively to evaluate concepts at various levels of representation.

Feedback from students and professional industrial users indicated that the method is useful for informing an ongoing design process, as well as for bringing attention to previously unconsidered aspects of product perception. All products may not incorporate all senses/perceptual modes, but the method can successfully be used to highlight opportunities and bring attention to modes other than the apparent visual properties of product appearance. Consequently this method provides application beyond design, providing value to other fields involved in product innovation and development.

References

Bonapace, Lisa (2000). "Pleasure-based human factors and the SEQUAM: sensorial quality assessment method". Proceedings of Design+Research, Milan, 261-271

Burnham, H. Douglas (2006). "Immanuel Kant (1724-1804): Theory of Aesthetics and Teleology (The Critique of Judgment)". The Internet Encyclopaedia of Philosophy, <http://www.iep.utm.edu/>, 2006-04-14.

Desmet, Pieter M. A. (2002). *Designing Emotions*. Delft: Delft University of Technology

Goldman, A. (2001). "The Aesthetic". In B. Gaut and D. McIver Lopes (Eds.), *The Routledge companion to aesthetics* (pp. 181-192). London: Routledge.

Goldstein, E. Bruce (2002). *Sensation and Perception*, 6th Edition, Pacific Grove, CA: Wadsworth

Hekkert, P. (2006). "Design aesthetics: Principles of pleasure in product design". In press. URL: <http://studiolab.io.tudelft.nl/hekkert/publications> [2006-04-05]

Jordan, Patrick (2000). *Designing Pleasurable Products*. London: Taylor & Francis

Jordan, Patrick (2002). *How to Make Brilliant Stuff That People Love & Make Big Money Out of It*. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons Ltd.

Liu, Yili (2003). "Engineering aesthetics and aesthetic ergonomics: Theoretical foundations and a dual-process methodology". *Ergonomics*, Vol. 46, Nos. 13/14, 1273-1292

Merriam-Webster (2006). Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary. Merriam-Webster, Inc. URL: <http://www.m-w.com/> [2006-04-05]

Norman, Donald A. (2004). *Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things*. Basic Books